

Youth, Culture & Sports

July 2024

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region's economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find the results of the second round of data collection during 2023 and the first months of 2024 and a comparison with the baseline data collected in the previous round.

In terms of Youth, Culture and Sports, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Youth with above basic overall digital skills in 2021 and 2023” and on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Youth with above basic overall digital skills in 2021 and 2023 (in percent)

Note
Data for Albania (2023), Kosovo* and North Macedonia (2023) not available

Source
Eurostat, [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ISOC_SK_DSKL_I21\\$DV_1201/default/table?lang=en](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ISOC_SK_DSKL_I21$DV_1201/default/table?lang=en) (accessed 6 February 2024).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicator

Ministerial Meeting on Culture
--

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

	Integration & stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives		Regional cooperation and people-to-people exchanges	
	Full association in Erasmus+ Programme			
Albania	Increased number of projects and mobilities implemented Not fully associated to the Programme			
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of projects and mobilities implemented Not fully associated to the Programme			
Kosovo*	Increased number of projects and mobilities implemented Not fully associated to the Programme			
Montenegro	No Information on projects and mobility provided Not fully associated to the Programme			
North Macedonia	Increased number of hubs and partnerships Fully associated to the Programme			
Serbia	Increased number of hubs and partnerships Fully associated to the Programme			

Legend: Information not available

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Highlights

Increased participation in the Erasmus+ programme
Continuous contribution to the European Week of Sport

